

D2.5

Interim Report

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Background to the legumES project

The legumES will ensure:

1. the uptake of best practices in agrobiodiverse legume-based cropped systems;
2. the uptake of methodologies and tools to quantify and balance the environmental and economic ecosystem service (ES) benefits provided by legumes;
3. that the ES benefits and cost offered by legumes are quantified across scales from field, farm, regional, national, and global levels; and
4. ES will be assessed to identify those conditions which are able to meet the EU targets: to decrease agrichemical inputs and losses, combat climate change, reverse biodiversity loss, and ensure the best nutritional provisioning.

To achieve this, legumES offers a multi-disciplinary consortium comprising 22 partners from 12 EU- and third countries (UK, CH) and including: 7, academic institutions; 6, Research and Technology Organizations; 5, SMEs (or micro-SMEs); 2, non-governmental organisations; and 2, large commercial companies. The individuals comprising legumES offer skills which include: agricultural-crop and -environment (ES) monitoring, life cycle assessment, economic- and socioeconomic-modelling, social-science, EU-agricultural and environmental policy, and law, plus decision support systems. The legumES research and innovation strategy centres on the use of a multi actor action-research approach, that is, where legume-facing stakeholders, and especially producers though all value chains actors, can 'operate', 'collaborate' and, 'reflect critically' on the measured ES benefits and costs of legume-based cropped systems, including legumes use in marginal lands; so that an optimal balance of ES can be achieved with success locally, and globally. To help achieve this, legumES also centres activities on a suite of 25 innovative legume-based PSs which use a wide range of legume species and types, plus different cropping approaches and linked value chains spanning the pedoclimatic regions of Europe.

For more information on the project, see:

- [Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumes, and legume-based cropped systems | LegumES | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission](#)
- www.legumESproject.eu

Executive Summary

The purpose of D2.5 is to reflect on the activities and approach of WP2 and ensure that future progress is in alignment with developing project needs and findings. This includes considering the integration of WP2 outcomes with the activities of other WPs. As such, this deliverable summarises the prioritisation of ES Indicators (ESI) and more specifically ESI methods (ESIMs) for use within WP2 and their development for use in agricultural systems. This prioritisation is informed by the multi actor approach (MAA) activities within WP1, and life cycle assessment modelling tasks based largely within WP3, though also WP4. Steps towards integrating ESIMs into downstream WP6 activities are also discussed.

It should be noted that as many Pilot Study systems are currently in-progress via multi-year experiments, and a synthesis on the *impacts and optimisation* of legume inclusion ES delivery in Pilot Study systems is not included here.

D2.5 first considers ESI priorities as identified from WP1 led MAA workshops and progress on the development of ESI/ESIMs (where required), and subsequent prioritisation of ESIMs for land managers (farmers, advisors and AES monitoring stakeholders). Finally, D2.5 summarises how these insights relate to downstream project activities, and future development of ESI/ESIMs (where required). Recommendations regarding use of ESIM for project activities are made throughout this report, summarised on the following page.

The full list of ESIMs (Annex 1), may also be of use to other research initiatives aiming to monitor legume integration into cropping systems.

Recommendation 1: It is important to equip decision makers in legume inclusive production systems to understand the value of within-farming-business benefits from legume related ES delivery, and to optimize systems to deliver ES that could be incentivized from external sources in the future. Therefore agri-environmental scheme (AES), or any added value scheme, regulators for service delivery should also be targeted as a potential user of WP2 outputs in addition to farmers and advisors.

Recommendation 2: Valorisation of N dynamics, protein, and crop yield quality should be prioritized. This does not preclude raising awareness of other potential ES benefits, and ways to monitor a wide range of ES delivery is likely needed to match a broad range of priorities across different countries.

Recommendation 3: ES monitoring framework should consider the likely tradeoff between interpretability and sensitivity, with cost and efficiency. Considering how to use ESIMs in combination, or in sequence may aid in alleviating these tradeoffs.

Recommendation 4: System management indicators rely on appropriate practice – accurate checking for compaction, reduced disease pressure, or reduced N. The Theory of Change should consider the direct incentivization of the practice or the incentivization/legislation of the management index to encourage uptake of the practice.

Recommendation 5: Many ESIMs present the opportunity to be utilized as ground truthing for remote sensing development or image analysis, but perhaps beyond the scope of the current project.

Recommendation 6: Guidance on using ESIMs should include guidance on the appropriate interpretation of indicators depending on the indicator type and whether a counter-factual (i.e. on farm trials, field or farm comparisons etc.) are available.

Considerations from National Multi Actor Workshops

WP2 focuses mainly on supporting the inclusion and optimisation of legumes into production systems; plus marginal land. Direct outputs are therefore aimed at “on the ground” decision makers as the main actors within these systems (i.e., farmers and advisors). However, as demonstrated through the national multi actor workshops (MAWs) led by WP1 and initial policy scanning activities led by WP5 (Batur, Balazs and Neulinger, 2025; Karley *et al.*, 2025), the wider value chain and the policy landscape will also influence the choice of these actors. As such, the MAW reports were consulted to ensure that WP2 outputs consider priorities from a range of influencing actors (policy makers, industry, and researchers).

General trends across the MAW reports included:

- incentivisation of legume production was seen as a key potential driver of legume ES valorisation across several countries, although wider policy scanning activities also highlight that enabling market development, promoting sustainable practices, raising consumer awareness, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing, and integrating policies are also likely to be required. It should also be noted that the desire to understand the economic value of ES benefits on farm, by farmers (i.e. within-business), was also highlighted. The use of legume must be profitable compared to alternatives.
- The ES benefits most highly prioritised across countries were biological nitrogen (N) fixation (BNF) benefits/soil fertility, protein production and produce quality. Other benefits such as biodiversity support, GHG emission mitigation, water quality improvement etc ranked more variably across the countries. This may reflect local drivers.
- All the MAWs identified ES benefits that can be categorised into the structure utilised for T2.1, as summarised in Deliverable 2.1 (N dynamics; productivity (yield) or yield qualities; soil qualities; C storage, and GHG; water quality, flood and erosion control; biodiversity (support, including pollinator support); and, pest, weed & disease management).

The MAW reports therefore suggest that incentivisation of legume integration into production systems, based on country specific prioritised outcomes would likely play a role in increasing legume ES valorisation. Influence of N dynamics and protein production in systems were seen as key benefits. Initial project policy dialogues also conclude that, *“There is a strong consensus on the need for systematic monitoring of legume-related ecosystem services. A proper monitoring system should be outcome-based, farm-led, low-cost, and should cover soil health, biodiversity, GHG emissions, productivity, and public health indicators”* (Batur, Balazs and Neulinger, 2025). Thus, whilst the Theory of Change to valorise legume ES will be delivered towards the latter stages of the legumES project, monitoring ES delivery on a site-by-site basis is likely to be important based on the following understanding.

- If incentives contribute to the valorisation of legume related ES, then it is important that value for money of ES delivery is considered which may include checking whether intended benefits were achieved. This may require monitoring by those incentivising Agri Environment Schemes (AES) or by any service payment (public or private) schemes.
- If maximising agronomic and economic benefits on farm for agricultural production contribute to the valorisation of legume related ES (e.g. reducing N rates whilst maintaining output to result in an improvement of gross margin), then it is important that farmers and advisors can monitor the crop systems in an appropriate manner so as to get the highest value of such

services in their situation (i.e within-farming-business) and be confident that the system is likely to support the desired benefits.

- If on farm demonstration and peer to peer learning is to support the awareness of legume ES benefits, then system changes must be confidently tracked and demonstrated by farms.

Recommendation 1: It is important to equip decision makers in legume inclusive production systems to understand the value of within-farming-business benefits from legume related ES delivery, and to optimize systems to deliver ES that could be incentivized from external sources in the future. Therefore agri-environmental scheme (AES), or any added value scheme, regulators for service delivery should also be targeted as a potential user of WP2 outputs in addition to farmers and advisors.

Recommendation 2: Valorisation of N dynamics, protein, and crop yield quality should be prioritized. This does not preclude raising awareness of other potential ES benefits, and ways to monitor a wide range of ES delivery is likely needed to match a broad range of priorities across different countries.

1. “Logical sieve” of ESIM for land managers

1.1 Background

T2.4 aims to build awareness and capacity to enable best use of legume-based solutions at a site-by-site level through supporting a “measure to manage” approach of ES delivery. Common barriers for monitoring and management systems for on farm decision include cost and ease of interpretation (Wall, Redmond and Kendall, 2023). The following activity aimed to use a “logical sieve” approach to rank the methods for monitoring ES delivery in legume systems in terms of ‘robustness’, ‘practicability’ and ‘applicability’ - the latter being the ability to detect meaningful changes in the capacity of legumes to deliver the following ES or ES benefits (as categorized by T2.1 and cross checked with the multi-actor workshop results).

- N dynamics;
- productivity or quality;
- soil quality, C storage and GHG;
- water qualities, including flood and erosion control;
- biodiversity (support, including for pollinator’s and other beneficial insects); and,
- pest, weed and disease management

1.2 Approach

A logical sieve was carried out as per Newall Price (*et al.*, 2020), adapted from Ritz (*et al.*, 2009), with the following modifications.

- The logical sieve was carried out on ESI Methods (ESIMs) rather than ESI. This is because ESI may be investigated through different methods ranging in ease of use and robustness, and ESIMs could be interpreted to provide information on several different ES benefits. Given that a wide range of ES prioritised are available, ESIMs which describe multiple ES will be beneficial.
- A pre-screening process was carried out due the large number of ESIMs.
- As legumes can be utilized in a range of ways for agricultural systems, the process must be carried out with the perspective of the following use cases:
 - **If the legume is acting as a cash crop** (*the perspective that the legume crop’s use is to be harvested to produce a valuable product, not excluding use for feed on farm*).
 - **If the legume is acting as a support to another crop** (*the perspective that the legume crop’s use is to support another crop on farm, e.g. supporting an intercrop or a following crop, including cover or catch crops, or as field margins*).
 - **If the legume’s use is for improvement of non-productive landscapes** (*the perspective that the legume crop is not grown on land cultivated for production but could be used for e.g. biodiversity enhancement or ecosystem restoration/climate adaptation*).
 - **If the legume is used as feed by grazing** (*the perspective that a legume crop is grown and livestock graze it directly, including legume rich swards. Impacts on the land the legumes are grown on are considered*).
 - **If the legume is used as a livestock feed** - not directly grazed (*the perspective that legumes are incorporated into livestock feed, but the livestock do not graze on the feed*

directly e.g. grain legumes incorporated into compound feeds. For clarification, the land the legumes are cultivated on is not considered here as this is considered in the other categories).

ESIMs were compiled from various sources, including:

- legumES WP2 activities (historic & present/future Pilot Study data surveys, and Pilot Study Work Programmes including those that have resulted in farmer targeted methodological protocols already (White *et al.*, 2022; Hawes *et al.*, 2025));
- methods related to T2.1 ES delivery categories identified from previous projects aimed at supporting farmers, advisors and AES stakeholders in monitoring and managing ES and production systems (e.g. NUTRI-CHECK NET (*NUTRI-CHECK NET Platform*), DIVERSIFY (Kiær *et al.*, 2020) and SUPER-G (Newall Price *et al.*, 2020)); and,
- screening from the legumES T3.1 literature review which screened over 25 previous legume related projects, as summarised in Cimarelli *et al.*, (2025).

The list was supplemented and cross validated through expert input and elicitation (Pilot Study and WP leads). Where ESIM details were not perceived to be common knowledge amongst the reviewers, examples of methods from literature and grey literature were collated provide enough detail for scoring. Following the resolving of similar ESIMs together, 218 were identified in total. After pre-screening, **the number of ESIMs was reduced to 133** (Annex 1). In short, ESIMs were pre-screened by scoring the ability of the method to be carried out by land managers, i.e. whether the indicator can be carried out in a commercial setting without the technical, financial and interpretive support from a research organisation. For the purposes of this activity, an expert was defined as “someone possessing extensive knowledge or ability in the domain, based on their qualifications, experience (at least 5 years) and occupation” (Table 1). Since experts believed that an ESIM able to represent multiple ES benefits across different legume-use cases would be particularly valuable, all ESIMs were evaluated against all the challenge criteria in the logical sieve.

Table 1. Expert reviewers. Expert reviewers were chosen to represent knowledge on key ES benefits (N dynamics; Productivity or quality; Soil quality, C storage and GHG; Water quality, flood and erosion control; Biodiversity; Pest, weed & disease management) from across Temperate, Continental and Mediterranean agro-climatic zones.

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Experts scored ESIMs for which they are confident they have sufficient knowledge and expertise. The resulting list of indicators methods then underwent screening against the following criteria:

- 1) **Relevance to each legume-use case** (legume is acting as a cash crop; legume is acting as a support to another crop; legume supporting non-productive landscapes; legume is used as feed by grazing; legume is used as a livestock feed - not directly grazed) (Table 2).

Table 2. Criterion 1) Is the indicator relevant to agricultural legume-use cases?

Use case	Score
Legume is acting as a cash crop	0=not relevant; 1=relevant
Legume is acting as a support to another crop (e.g supporting an intercrop or a following crop, including cover and catch crops, or field margin)	0=not relevant; 1=relevant
If the legume’s use is for biodiversity enhancement or ecosystem restoration/climate adaptation of non-productive landscapes	0=not relevant; 1=relevant
Legume is used as feed by grazing	0=not relevant; 1=relevant
Legume is used as a livestock feed - not directly grazed	0=not relevant; 1=relevant

2) **Relevance to ES delivery/benefits.** Cross checked that at minimum, this covers the ES benefits highlighted through the MAWs (N dynamics; productivity (yield) or yield qualities; Soil qualities, including C storage and GHG; water qualities, including via flood and erosion control; biodiversity (support, including for pollinators and support beneficial insects); and, pest, weed, and disease management) (Table 3). This is to ensure that any handbooks cover the topic areas likely to be of interest to land managers, advisors and policy makers.

Table 3. Criterion 2) Is the indicator relevant to ES delivery/benefits categorised in legumES?

ES	Score
N dynamics;	0=not relevant; 1=poor indicator; 2=relevant; 3 = highly relevant
Productivity (yield) or yield qualities;	0=not relevant; 1=poor indicator; 2=relevant; 3 = highly relevant
Soil qualities, including C storage and GHG;	0=not relevant; 1=poor indicator; 2=relevant; 3 = highly relevant
Water qualities, including via flood and erosion control;	0=not relevant; 1=poor indicator; 2=relevant; 3 = highly relevant
Biodiversity (support, including for pollinators and beneficial insects);	0=not relevant; 1=poor indicator; 2=relevant; 3 = highly relevant
Pest, weed, and disease management	0=not relevant; 1=poor indicator; 2=relevant; 3 = highly relevant

3) **Challenge criteria included (Table 4):**

- Interpretability
- Sensitivity
- Practicability
- Efficiency & cost
- Geographical coverage
- Availability of baseline & threshold data
- Comprehensibility & clarity

Table 4. Criterion 3) Does the indicator meet the following challenge criteria?

Challenge criteria	Score
1. Interpretability a) Is the indicator interpretable in quantitative terms as an indicator of ES delivery and temporal change in ecosystem function?	0 = Not interpretable; 1 = Interpretable in qualitative terms (ordinal/nominal/categorical data); 2

Challenge criteria	Score
b) Is it clear what interpretation can or cannot be placed on the indicator?	= Interpretable using continuous quantitative data,
2. Sensitivity a) Is the indicator responsive to changes in land management? b) What is the probability of detecting ‘significant’ changes between sampling intervals? For quantitative data, consider likely degree of change over a sampling interval and magnitude of random error such as 95% confidence intervals	0 = Not likely; 1 = Likely for large changes (e.g. 50-400% increase / 50-90% decrease); 2 = Likely for small changes (e.g. 10-25% increase or decrease),
3.1. Practicability for benchmarking (farmers & advisers) a) How practicable is the indicator for use on farm? b) Are there robust, proven methods for its measurement? c) Are such methods available now or will they need considerable development?	0 = not practicable; 1 = potentially practicable; 2 = practicable.
3.2. Practicability for AES or national monitoring (researchers & policy makers) a) How practicable is the indicator for use as part of a monitoring programme? b) Are there robust, proven methods for its measurement? c) Are such methods available now or will they need considerable development?	0 = not practicable; 1 = potentially practicable; 2 = practicable.

1.3 Weightings and evaluation

To select the most appropriate indicator methods to use by farmers, advisors and those carrying out “on the ground” AES monitoring, the following evaluation scheme was used for each ES and legume-use combination. An additional calculation step was added compared to Newall Price *et al.*, (2020) to account for multiple legume-use cases. For instance, if most expert reviewers judged an ESIM to be relevant for a given legume-use case, then the following approach was applied. First, for each legume-use case (Table 2), the score for each criterion associated with that ESIM was calculated using the mean of the reviewers’ responses to the corresponding challenge criteria. Second, this score was weighted by the relevance of the ESIM to the specific ES topic, ensuring that indicators which aligned more strongly with certain ES topics were appropriately emphasised.

- i. For each ES, the “short-listed” ESIMs were then assessed by the task leader and each ES lead using the following criteria.
 - ESIMs that were not considered to be relevant to legume-use cases were given lower priority during the selection process.
 - ESIMs considered to be insufficiently interpretable or comprehensible by farmers and advisers were excluded from further consideration, based on the following criteria.
 - Are there well-established practical protocols for the ESIM or can they be developed with reasonable effort?
 - Is the indicator responsive to management?
 - Is the ESIM relatively cheap, practical and simple to measure?
 - Are the measurements associated with the ESIM practicable?
 - Is the indicator policy relevant?

- Is the amount of sampling support and sampling intensity required to determine the indicator reasonable?
 - ESIMs that were perceived to be closely related were resolved together to increase diversity of ESIMs shortlisted.
- ii. All the “short-listed” ESIMs that returned a positive response to the above questions were retained in the final short list. Several similar ESIMs were ranked closely together (for example yield via combine harvester, or yield via quadrat) suggesting limitations for the logical sieve approach in separating ESIMs that describe the same, or similar ESI. Where this occurred, experts chose the most appropriate method to shortlist. Several ESIMs were added to the shortlist based on priorities identified via the MAWs.

1.4 Results & Discussion

Overall, the ESIMs showed positive correlations across the average challenge criteria scores. Strong positive relationships were observed between “Interpretability” and “Sensitivity,” as well as between “Comprehensibility & clarity for farmers” and “Comprehensibility & clarity for AES.” In contrast, the most pronounced negative associations occurred between “Practicability for benchmarking (farmers)” and “Sensitivity,” followed by “Efficiency and cost” and “Sensitivity.” These negative relationships reflect the inherent trade-off between the value of highly sensitive- indicators and practical barriers to their adoption, particularly efficiency and cost (Wall, Redmond and Kendall, 2023) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Correlation matrix of average challenge criteria scores across ESIMs.

	Interpretability	Sensitivity	Practicability for benchmarking (farmers)	Practicability for AES	Efficiency and cost	Geographical coverage	Availability of baseline & threshold data	Comprehensibility & clarity - for farmers	Comprehensibility & clarity - for AES
Interpretability	1.00	0.53	0.00	0.07	-0.13	-0.03	0.28	0.40	0.48
Sensitivity		1.00	-0.21	-0.09	-0.20	0.09	0.47	0.39	0.46
Practicability for benchmarking (farmers)			1.00	0.47	0.72	0.37	0.07	0.34	0.07
Practicability for AES				1.00	0.38	0.15	0.00	0.22	0.33
Efficiency and cost					1.00	0.36	-0.03	0.28	0.06
Geographical coverage						1.00	0.44	0.34	0.25
Availability of baseline & threshold data							1.00	0.41	0.30
Comprehensibility & clarity - for farmers								1.00	0.82
Comprehensibility & clarity - for AES									1.00

Many of the landscape social value indicators extracted from Newall Price *et al.* (2020) (ESIMs 258-271, see Annex) were scored as not relevant to the agronomically focused ES benefit categories outlined within this task. This suggests little overlap exists between landscape related social benefit indicators and indicators of agronomic benefits. More overlap may have occurred if productivity was broadened to include farm income and therefore potential diversification streams, or potentially included cultural aspects of production, such as impacts on grower mental health, aesthetic expectations of the working environment, workload management, or how production activities serve heritage, cultural norms, and rural development. The development and monitoring of indicators in these areas are likely to require concerted effort to identify and monitor, above the level of individual farm businesses and local land management decision makers, and so were not considered in this approach, but should be a target for future development. Amongst ES sub-topic discussions, it was also highlighted that certain ESIMs may benefit from being combined. Some legume-use cases returned fewer relevant ESIMs than others, resulting in less than ten shortlisted ESIMs being selected for legume-use case/ES benefit topic combinations.

Greater overlap was observed among the different legume-use cases than among the various ES benefit categories. This indicates that, for stakeholders, guidance on using ESIMs would be more effectively organised by ES benefit rather than by legume-use case, at least initially, to provide a more streamlined and efficient structure.

1.4.1 N dynamics

The highest ranked “N dynamics” indicator methods are summarised in Table 5, considering not only N related ES benefits (such as reduced N requirements for following crops), but also potential dis-benefits such as N leaching risk. Generally, the highest ranked ESIMs across use cases were similar, except for the use of legumes as non-grazed feed (where experts considered that many field level N dynamics indicators were not relevant and as such this category is omitted from the summary table), and for non-productive landscapes, which included ESIMs that may be related to decomposition and thus mineralisation rates of the soil.

There was considerable overlap between N dynamics ESIMs shortlisted for cash crops, grazed legumes and legumes as supporting crops, perhaps due to the inherent understanding that many N dynamics benefits of legumes as cash crops will be realised in the following crops and across the rotation. For these use cases, ESIMs that describe N inputs/outputs ranked highly, potentially due to the perceived low cost of calculating these metrics from farm management data (N rates, yield etc.) rather than direct measurements. It was noted, however, that whilst these ESIMs describe the management of the system, which relate to the wider benefits that the system may deliver (such as reduced GHG emissions from N fertiliser use), information on the ES processes that underpin those benefits (such as BNF, N residue mineralisation rates and availability to following crops, and changes to following crop yield potential etc.) may be masked if management decisions are not precise enough (for example, if N rates are applied above the following crops economic optimum N rate). It is therefore important to also utilise ESIMs that describe the ES benefit potential (such as soil N supply where possible).

Remote sensing technology other than machinery mounted (e.g., handheld or remote sensing) was not shortlisted, perhaps due to perceived up-front costs, or perceived further development to translate results and calibrations across different crop types. Nevertheless, these technologies provide promising avenues for further development, especially when an upfront cost is spread across large production areas. Modelled N provision from non-harvested residues was selected, although the

reviewers are aware that several models exist and none are currently universally accepted (Constantin *et al.*, 2024; Mouritzen *et al.*, 2025), perhaps due to similar reasons and with similar future opportunities.

It was also highlighted that combinations of ESIMs may improve interpretability and sensitivity, although this may increase costs and reduce efficiency. For example, grain nutrient analysis can be used to calculate N offtake from crops and therefore increase the accuracy of soil surface N balance estimations, or yield could be combined with remote sensing of total biomass and/or dynamic crop modelling to better estimate the N residues returned to the system. Remote sensing, and increased integration of digital solutions (such as yield mapping) could provide opportunities to alleviate these potential trade-offs through development. Multiple ESIMs could also be used to create a hierarchical monitoring framework to make most efficient use of farmer and advisor resources. For example, dynamic crop modelling, or legume performance could be used to infer high or low N provision likelihood, which could then be followed up with more accurate methods (such as direct legume tissue N measurements, soil mineral N (SMN) testing etc.) to inform agronomic decision making at a reduced financial burden to the farmer or advisor.

Nodulation scores were only shortlisted for non-productive legume systems, possibly due to perceived low efficiency and poor interpretability compared to other ESIMs relevant to productive systems. Further investigation on whether nodulation scores can be related to biological N fixation rates will aid in understanding the potential of nodulation scores as a useful tool for farmers.

Notably, soil N leachate analysis through porous pots (due to perceived high cost and low efficiency and practicability) and soil nitrate sensors were not shortlisted, although the expert reviewers highlighted that practicability and comprehensibility may increase for soil sensors as validation and method standardisation increases; and, as purchase and annual deployment prices decreases. The reviewers were aware of the overlap between legume impacts on N dynamic and other ES categories, including, for example, legume impacts on estimated GHG emissions through reduced N fertiliser inputs to the rotation.

Table 5. The ten highest ranked “N dynamics” indicators for different legume-use cases. Use cases: CC = if legume is acting as a cash crop; SC = If legume is acting as a supporting crop; NP = if legume’s use us for improvement of non-productive landscapes; GF = if legume is used as feed by grazing; NGF = if legume is used as a livestock feed – not directly grazed.

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
CC	ESIM 215_N input rate (kg N/ha)	1
	ESIM 055_N use efficiency calculations (e.g., kg N/t yield)	2
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (kg NO3- & NH3 /ha)	3
	ESIM 015_Following crop soil N supply - measured uptake (kg N/ha)	4
	ESIM 213_N surplus on soil surface balance (kg N/ha)	5
	ESIM 080_Grain protein analysis - following crops (%)	6
	ESIM 110_Potential mineralizable N (kg NO3- & NH3 /ha, available and potential)	7
	ESIM 044_Non-harvested residue N content - modelled (kg N/ha)	8
	ESIM 024_Grain protein content (kg/ha)	9
	ESIM 081_Nil N plot in following crop coupled with in season monitoring of N requirement (NUE metrics/required N rate)	10

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
SC	ESIM 215_N input rate (kg N/ha)	1
	ESIM 055_N use efficiency calculations (e.g kg N/t yield)	2
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (jg NO3- & NH3 /ha)	3
	ESIM 215_N input rate (kg N/ha)	4
	ESIM 015_Following crop soil N supply - measured uptake (kg N/ha)	5
	ESIM 227_Quantities of manure applied (t/ha)	6
	ESIM 213_N surplus on soil surface balance (kg N/ha)	7
	ESIM 080_Grain protein analysis - following crops (%)	8
	ESIM 110_Potential mineralizable N (kg NO3- & NH3 /ha, available and potential)	9
	ESIM 044_Non-harvested residue N content - modelled (kg N/ha)	10
NP	ESIM 149_N use efficiency (fertiliser) (% (N input/N output))	1
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (kg NO3- & NH3 /ha)	2
	ESIM 110_Potential mineralizable N (kg NO3- & NH3 /ha, available and potential)	3
	ESIM 301_Nodulation score (Proportion of pink nodules; proportion of large nodules; number of nodules)	4
	ESIM 114_Mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) carbon fractions (C %/kg dry soil)	5
	ESIM 010_Soil organic matter content (LOI) (%/kg dry soil)	6
	ESIM 077_Buffer strip size and quality (length per km2 OR % area)	7
	ESIM 089_"soil health" analysis - e.g Haney test (index)	8
	ESIM 008_Tea bags for litter decomposition ((g) lost / day)	9
	ESIM 279_Cotton strip assay for measuring litter decomposition ((g) lost / day)	10
GF	ESIM 215_N input rate (kg N/ha)	1
	ESIM 055_N use efficiency calculations (e.g., kg N/t yield)	2
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (Kg NO3- & NH3 /ha)	3
	ESIM 015_Following crop soil N supply - measured uptake (kg N/ha)	4
	ESIM 227_Quantities of manure applied (t/ha)	5
	ESIM 213_N surplus on soil surface balance (kg N/ha)	6
	ESIM 080_Grain protein analysis - following crops (%)	7
	ESIM 110_Potential mineralizable N (kg NO3- & NH3 /ha, available and potential)	8
	ESIM 044_Not-harvested residue N content - modelled (kg N/ha)	9
	ESIM 079_Tractor mounted N sensors (Spectral indices OR kg/ha)	10

1.4.2 Productivity or quality

The highest ranked “Productivity (yield) or yield qualities” indicator methods are summarised in Table 6. Many of the ESIMs for productivity are direct measures of the ES, for example grain yield, grain protein content and value of the crop depending on the end market. As such, many measures of production are related to established indicators which are well accepted by the supply chain. Hence the diversity and thus number of different relevant ESIMs were lower than in other ES topic areas. Nonetheless, providing guidance on obtaining the most accurate measurements possible will help

improve the overall quality of production data. It should also be recognised that the parameters influencing endmarket- value can be broad, such as visual quality, seed size, insect damage, and processing characteristics, and may themselves comprise multiple underlying measurements. These, in turn, often depend on the specific requirements of the intended end market.

Although end-market value was prioritised in the logical sieve, gross margin analysis was not. This may reflect the perceived effort required to calculate total farm business costs and express them on a per-area and per-crop basis. Simplifying gross margin to “end-market value” minus “variable input costs” may make this ESIM more practicable for users.

To assess the contribution of legumes as supporting crops, indicators relating to the productivity and quality of supported crops, such as yield and protein content, were ranked highly. However, these ESIMs do not inherently capture changes in the productivity of a supported bicrop (i.e., ‘intercrops’) without additional work. Land use efficiency metrics such as the ‘Land Equivalent Ratio’ (or ‘Partial Equivalence Ratio’) and ‘Transgressive Overyielding Index’ etc were considered relevant to supporting crop effects but were not ranked highly because of the perceived impracticality of growing and assessing each component of a bicrop separately to quantify performance. Despite this limitation, no more practical alternatives were identified, and therefore Land Use Ratios were retained in the shortlist. Although not shortlisted, ESIMs relating to pollinator populations and floral resources were scored as relevant to productivity and quality. This highlights that flowering species may also contribute to honey production, even within “nonproductive” landscapes.

In livestock production systems that incorporate legumes as feed, whether grazed directly or not, the highest-ranked ESIMs were, once again, direct indicators of production performance. Nutrient analysis of legume feedstocks was also included in the shortlist following panel discussion, although it is acknowledged that such analyses may be perceived as costly. Ongoing development of standard reference values for legume feed quality, as well as improved calibration of lower-cost analytical methods such as NIR, would support more confident and financially accessible integration of new legume species and mixtures into livestock diets. Daily live-weight gain did not initially progress through the pre-screening stage, which may reflect differences in how its practicability is perceived across various farming systems.

Table 6. The five highest ranked “Productivity or quality” indicators for different legume-use cases. Use cases: CC = If legume is acting as a cash crop; SC = If legume is acting as a supporting crop; NP = if legume’s use us for improvement of non-productive landscapes; GF = if legume is used as feed by grazing; NGF = if legume is used as a livestock feed – not directly grazed.

Use Case	Indicator method	Ranking (within use case)
CC	ESIM PFC_C_1_Yield – seed - commercial combine harvester (t/ha and moisture content (%))	1
	ESIM 304_End market value of legume seed (Euros/t)	2
	ESIM 024_Grain Protein Content (kg/ha)	3
	ESIM 149_N use efficiency (fertiliser) (% (N input/N output))	4
	ESIM 045_Quality - visual appearance (%)	5
SC	ESIM PFC_C_1_Yield – seed - commercial combine harvester (t/ha & moisture content (%))	1
	ESIM 304_End market value of legume seed (Euros/t)	2

Use Case	Indicator method	Ranking (within use case)
	ESIM 080_Grain protein analysis - following crops (%)	3
	ESIM PFC_C_2_Yield – seed- quadrats (t/ha, and moisture content (%))	4
	ESIM 149_N use efficiency (fertiliser) (% (N input/N output))	5
	ESIM 035_Land use efficiency ratios (ratio)	Shortlisted post discussion
GF	ESIM 091_Forage or Feed efficiency - Milk production (L (milk)/cow)	1
	ESIM PFC_C_3_Yield– forage crops - quadrats (t/ha & moisture content (%))	2
	ESIM 092_Forage or silage quality for feed (multiple)	3
	ESIM 149_N use efficiency (fertiliser) (% (N input/N output))	4
	ESIM 20_Forage or feed efficiency - livestock daily live weight gain (Growth rate (kg/day))	Shortlisted post discussion
NGF	ESIM 023_Grain yield (t/ha)	1
	ESIM 091_Forage or Feed efficiency - Milk production (litres/cow)	2
	ESIM 024_Grain Protein Content (Kg/ha)	3
	ESIM 092_Forage or silage quality for feed (Multiple)	Shortlisted post discussion
	ESIM 302_Seed quality as feed (Multiple)	Shortlisted post discussion
	ESIM 20_Forage or Feed efficiency - Livestock daily live weight gain (Growth rate (kg/day))	Shortlisted post discussion

1.4.3 Soil quality, C storage and GHG emissions

The highest ranked “Soil qualities, including for C storage and GHG emissions” indicator methods are listed in Table 7. Although grouped under a single category, assessments of soil qualities, carbon storage, and GHG will likely require different sets of indicators. For soil carbon storage specifically, reviewers emphasised that regular, long term soil C measurements are the most reliable approach for detecting changes over time. In contrast, interpreting effects in the short term remains considerably more challenging.

For GHG emissions, it is noted that no direct measurements of GHG emissions were selected as feasible for measurement by farmers and advisors. GHG calculations were also not shortlisted, potentially due to the low efficiency perceived of compiling data compared to indicators measuring soil quality and soil C storage. However, the reviewers are aware of several well established commercial calculators for use by farm businesses (Defra, 2023), and so GHG calculations have been included in the final list. Whilst the reviewers highlight that GHG calculators often rely on assumptions and standard values that can be continuously improved with further primary data capture, the use of GHG calculators can help record any potential benefits of changing in farm management practices due to the inclusion of legumes within the rotation (for example, by reducing the need for manufactured N fertiliser applications) and are already being used by partners, at the national level or as part of the European projects “ClieNFarms” or ‘Climate Farm Demo’ (101060212). It was highlighted that the limitations of using (farm level) carbon calculators, or any other tools that use standard coefficients and modelling assumptions (including N balances and Treatment Frequency indices etc.) to infer an impact of

including legumes into a system requires appropriate framing and careful interpretation, as any emissions or input reduction attributed to legumes is therefore mediated through management changes. To isolate legume impact, an explicit comparator rotation must be defined (i.e. legume-free), holding other variables constant wherever possible. In reality, farm systems rarely provide perfectly controlled comparisons, meaning calculators are most likely to capture system change rather than strictly legume-only effects. Guidance on using ESIMs should therefore also include guidance on the appropriate interpretation of indicators depending on the indicator type and whether a counterfactual (i.e. on farm trials, field or farm comparisons etc) are available.

Soil nutrient chemical analyses and variations of soil carbon measures were highly ranked, likely due to the perceived practicability of these for farmers and advisors due to a history of commercial availability.

Several physical soil measures were listed including: Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS); slake tests for aggregate stability; water infiltration rates; and, soil coring to visually inspect compaction and penetrometer resistance. Direct assessment of soil structural condition can provide a valuable baseline and enable long-term monitoring of changes resulting from new management practices. For example, any potential benefits arising from increased organic matter inputs may take several years to translate into measurable improvements in soil structure. Soil structural evaluations can also help determine whether the inclusion of legumes within a rotation has inadvertently led to declines in soil quality, for instance, if cultivation on wet soils has caused compaction, and can therefore identify where remedial action is required. Conversely, if the cultivation of deep-rooting legumes enhances soil structure, monitoring structural condition (such as the presence or absence of compaction layers) may allow producers to reduce unnecessary cultivations. Among decomposition based ESIMs, the cotton strip assay was ranked more highly than the tea bag test. This may reflect concerns about the practical challenges of sourcing the appropriate tea bag materials, an issue that was noted in several Participatory Trials within the current project.

Table 7. The ten highest ranked “Soil quality, C storage and GHG” indicators for different legume-use cases. Use cases: CC = If legume is acting as a cash crop; SC = If legume is acting as a supporting crop; NP = if legume’s use us for improvement of non-productive landscapes; GF = if legume is used as feed by grazing; NGF = if legume is used as a livestock feed – not directly grazed.

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
CC	ESIM 010_Soil organic matter content (LOI) (%/kg dry soil)	1
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 011_Slake test ((g) lost)	4
	ESIM 120_Soil organic carbon - Dumas method (SOC %/kg dry soil)	5
	ESIM 060_Soil penetration resistance - penetrometer (PSI & mm)	6
	ESIM 279_Cotton strip assay for measuring litter decomposition ((g) lost / day)	7
	ESIM 058_Soil nutrients - exchangeable P, K, Mg (mg/kg OR nutrient recommendation system index (index may differ between country))	8
	ESIM 114_Mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) carbon fractions (C %/kg dry soil)	9
	ESIM 072_Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores (Score)	10

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
SC	ESIM 010_Soil organic matter content (LOI) (%/kg dry soil)	1
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 120_Soil organic carbon - Dumas method (SOC %/kg dry soil)	4
	ESIM 060_Soil penetration resistance - penetrometer (PSI & mm)	5
	ESIM 279_Cotton strip assay for measuring litter decomposition ((g) lost / day)	6
	ESIM 058_Soil nutrients - exchangeable P, K, Mg (mg/kg OR nutrient recommendation system index (index may differ between country))	7
	ESIM 072_Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores (Score)	8
	ESIM 115_POM carbon fractions (SOC %/kg dry soil)	9
	ESIM 012_Water infiltration (ml/s)	10
NP	ESIM 010_Soil organic matter content (LOI) (%/kg dry soil)	1
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 011_Slake test ((g) lost)	4
	ESIM 120_Soil organic carbon - Dumas method (SOC %/kg dry soil)	5
	ESIM 060_Soil penetration resistance - penetrometer (PSI & mm)	6
	ESIM 279_Cotton strip assay for measuring litter decomposition ((g) lost / day)	7
	ESIM 058_Soil nutrients - exchangeable P, K, Mg (mg/kg OR nutrient recommendation system index (index may differ between country))	8
	ESIM 114_Mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) carbon fractions (C %/kg dry soil)	9
	ESIM 072_Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores (Score)	10
GF	ESIM 010_Soil organic matter content (LOI) (%/kg dry soil)	1
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 120_Soil organic carbon - Dumas method (SOC %/kg dry soil)	4
	ESIM 060_Soil penetration resistance - penetrometer (PSI & mm)	5
	ESIM 279_Cotton strip assay for measuring litter decomposition ((g) lost / day)	6
	ESIM 058_Soil nutrients - exchangeable P, K, Mg (mg/kg OR nutrient recommendation system index (index may differ between country))	7
	ESIM 072_Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores (Score)	8
	ESIM 115_POM carbon fractions (SOC %/kg dry soil)	9
	ESIM 012_Water infiltration (ml/s)	10

1.4.4 Water quality, flood and erosion control

The highest ranked “Water qualities, including for flood and erosion control” indicator methods are presented in Table 8. Overlap was shared with several ESIMs highlighted in Soil quality, C storage and GHG. Visual inspection of erosion features ranked highest in many use cases, and a scoring system is

currently being developed as part of the legumES project. Direct measures of water quality were not shortlisted, perhaps due to low perceived practicability by farmers, requirement of specific equipment, challenges of understanding influences on a small scale, or assumption that this would be monitored by other stakeholders (such as water management companies). However, soil P balance calculations and soil mineral N tests featured in the shortlist.

Table 8. The ten highest ranked “Water quality, flood and erosion control” indicators for different legume-use cases. Use cases: CC = If legume is acting as a cash crop; SC = If legume is acting as a supporting crop; NP = if legume’s use us for improvement of non-productive landscapes; GF = if legume is used as feed by grazing; NGF = if legume is used as a livestock feed – not directly grazed.

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
CC	ESIM 255_Number/Presence of erosion features (rills, gullies, landslides) - 1-Evidence of surface runoff / erosion pedestals / sediment deposition; 2-Evidence of rills; 3-Presence of gullies or eroded stream banks; 4-Presence of landslides/mass wasting; 5-Presence of piping (Y/N)	1
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 011_Slake test ((g) lost)	3
	ESIM 078_Ground cover - visual estimation (%)	4
	ESIM 061_Water consumption rates (Number of watering days, total water rate (L/ha/day), the cost of water (Euro/L).)	5
	ESIM 012_Water infiltration (mL/s)	6
	ESIM 014_Observed soil erosion risk (Y/N & severity)	7
	ESIM 073_Water use efficiency (m3 H2O/t)	8
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (Kg NO3- & NH3 /ha)	9
	ESIM 214_P surplus on soil surface balance (kg P/ha)	10
SC	ESIM 255_Number/Presence of erosion features (rills, gullies, landslides) - 1-Evidence of surface runoff / erosion pedestals / sediment deposition; 2-Evidence of rills; 3-Presence of gullies or eroded stream banks; 4-Presence of landslides/mass wasting; 5-Presence of piping (Y/N)	1
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 078_Ground cover - visual estimation (%)	3
	ESIM 061_Water consumption rates (Number of watering days, total water rate (l/ha/day), the cost of water (Euro/L).)	4
	ESIM 012_Water infiltration (mL/s)	5
	ESIM 014_Observed soil erosion risk (Y/N & severity)	6
	ESIM 073_Water use efficiency (m3 H2O/t)	7
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (Kg NO3- & NH3 /ha)	8
	ESIM 214_P surplus on soil surface balance (kg P/ha)	9
ESIM 072_Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores (Score)	10	
NP	ESIM 255_Number/Presence of erosion features (rills, gullies, landslides) - 1-Evidence of surface runoff / erosion pedestals / sediment deposition; 2-Evidence of rills; 3-Presence of gullies or eroded stream banks; 4-Presence of landslides/mass wasting; 5-Presence of piping (Y/N)	1

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 011_Slake test ((g) lost)	3
	ESIM 078_Ground cover - visual estimation (%)	4
	ESIM 012_Water infiltration (mL/s)	5
	ESIM 014_Observed soil erosion risk (Y/N & severity)	6
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (kg NO ₃ - & NH ₃ /ha)	7
	ESIM 072_Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores (Score)	8
	ESIM 240_Sealing / crusting presence (Y/N or %)	9
	ESIM 225_Ponding, standing water (Y/N OR % area)	10
GF	ESIM 255_Number/Presence of erosion features (rills, gullies, landslides) - 1-Evidence of surface runoff / erosion pedestals / sediment deposition; 2-Evidence of rills; 3-Presence of gullies or eroded stream banks; 4-Presence of landslides/mass wasting; 5-Presence of piping (Y/N)	1
	ESIM 009_Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) (Scale (1-5))	2
	ESIM 078_Ground cover - visual estimation (%)	3
	ESIM 061_Water consumption rates (Number of watering days, total water rate (l/ha/day), the cost of water (Euro/L).)	4
	ESIM 012_Water infiltration (mL/s)	5
	ESIM 014_Observed soil erosion risk (Y/N & severity)	6
	ESIM 073_Water use efficiency (m ³ H ₂ O/t)	7
	ESIM 026_Soil mineral N content (kg NO ₃ - & NH ₃ /ha)	8
	ESIM 214_P surplus on soil surface balance (kg P/ha)	9
ESIM 072_Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores (Score)	10	

1.4.5 Biodiversity (support, including pollinator support)

The highest ranked “Biodiversity (support, including for pollinators and other beneficial insects)” indicator methods are presented in Table 9. ESIMs that directly measured arthropod, soil macrofauna, bird, and botanical diversity were shortlisted, whereas those assessing soil microbial diversity were not. This may reflect perceptions of high cost (though costs may decrease with ongoing technological advances) and low comprehensibility among end users. ESIMs relating to soil microbial activity, such as soil respiration, were also not included in the shortlist. Overall, the ESIMs selected were broadly consistent across the different use cases.

Flowering duration was identified as a potential indicator of pollinator provision, although the reviewers note that whilst flowering availability throughout the year may relate to pollinator food sources, the availability of pollinator habitats must also be considered. Legume flowering duration could therefore be combined with other ESIMs not currently shortlisted such as buffer strip size, or other measures of nearby pollinator habitats drawing on farm maps and satellite imagery. The reviewers note that development of image analysis bioacoustics monitoring, arthropod identification aids, camera traps, or remote sensing of wider habitat diversity may aid in the practicability of biodiversity measures.

Table 9. The ten highest ranked “Biodiversity (support, including pollinator support)” indicators for different legume-use cases. Use cases: CC = If legume is acting as a cash crop; SC = If legume is acting as a supporting crop; NP = if legume’s use us for improvement of non-productive landscapes; GF = if legume is used as feed by grazing; NGF = if legume is used as a livestock feed – not directly grazed.

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
CC	ESIM 003_Pollinator transects (counts/m)	1
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 046_Bird monitoring (index)	4
	ESIM 178_Number of nesting sites for meadow birds (number/ha)	5
	ESIM PFC_C_5_Flowering duration (Dates)	6
	ESIM 076_Sweep netting for predatory insects (species list/index)	7
	ESIM 070_Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index (Index)	8
	ESIM 004_Pan traps for beneficial insects (species list/index)	9
	ESIM 071_Floral unit density for Estimation of nectariferous value from abundance of different flowers from plant species (Floral units/m2 (per each plant species))	10
SC	ESIM 003_Pollinator transects (counts/m)	1
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 046_Bird monitoring (index)	4
	ESIM 178_Number of nesting sites for meadow birds (number/ha)	5
	ESIM PFC_C_5_Flowering duration (Dates)	6
	ESIM 076_Sweep netting for predatory insects (species list/index)	7
	ESIM 070_Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index (Index)	8
	ESIM 004_Pan traps for beneficial insects (species list/index)	9
	ESIM 013_Flower Insect Timed counts (visits/minute)	10
NP	ESIM 003_Pollinator transects (counts/m)	1
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 046_Bird monitoring (index)	4
	ESIM 178_Number of nesting sites for meadow birds (number/ha)	5
	ESIM PFC_C_5_Flowering duration (Dates)	6
	ESIM 076_Sweep netting for predatory insects (species list/index)	7
	ESIM 004_Pan traps for beneficial insects (species list/index)	8
	ESIM 071_Floral unit density for Estimation of nectariferous value from abundance of different flowers from plant species (Floral units/m2 (per each plant species))	9
	ESIM 179_Mole hills (mole hills/ha OR mole hills/ha/yr)	10

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
GF	ESIM 003_Pollinator transects (counts/m)	1
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	2
	ESIM 006_Earthworm surveys (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM 046_Bird monitoring (index)	4
	ESIM 178_Number of nesting sites for meadow birds (number/ha)	5
	ESIM PFC_C_5_Flowering duration (Dates)	6
	ESIM 076_Sweep netting for predatory insects (species list/index)	7
	ESIM 070_Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index (Index)	8
	ESIM 004_Pan traps for beneficial insects (species list/index)	9
	ESIM 179_Mole hills (mole hills/ha OR mole hills/ha/y)	10

1.1.0. Pest, weed & disease management

The highest ranked “pest, weed, and disease management” indicator methods are presented in Table 10. Cimarelli et al., (2025) notes that pest, weed & disease management indicators are often observation based, which is reflected in the shortlisted ESIMs found here (the highest ranked ESIMs are often observations of foliar aspects of the plant). In similarity with N dynamic metrics, the measurement of management choices ranked highly, potentially due to the low cost and high efficiency of calculating the metric. Again, it is noted that this outcome relies on the accurate use of further management approaches, e.g. through IPM and economic pest threshold use for potential benefits to not be masked. Likewise for N dynamics, it may be perceived that Pest, Weed & disease management benefits inherently occur throughout the following crops and rotation, and as such ESIMs prioritised for legume cash crops have cross over with their potential to support further crops in the rotation, or in the case of the non-productive crops category perhaps through altering the properties of the landscapes surrounding cropped areas. Above canopy images ranked in several of the use cases on the assumption that technology may develop to automate image analysis and pest/weed/disease identification.

Table 10. The five highest ranked “Pest, weed & disease management” indicators for different legume-use cases. Use cases: CC = If legume is acting as a cash crop; SC = If legume is acting as a supporting crop; NP = if legume’s use us for improvement of non-productive landscapes; GF = if legume is used as feed by grazing; NGF = if legume is used as a livestock feed – not directly grazed.

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
CC	ESIM 083_Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - stem diseases (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	1
	ESIM 027_Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - leaf diseases (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	2
	ESIM 070_Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index (Index)	3
	ESIM 028_Grass weed head cover (Grass weed head cover (%) Grass weed head density (seed heads/m2))	4

Use Case	ESIM #_Indicator method (Units)	Ranking (within use case)
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	5
SC	ESIM 070_Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index (Index)	1
	ESIM 028_Grass weed head cover (Grass weed head cover (%) Grass weed head density (seed heads/m2))	2
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	3
	ESIM 064_Nematode counts (counts/m3)	4
	ESIM PFC_C_8_Above canopy image (image)	5
NP	ESIM 083_Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - stem diseases (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	1
	ESIM 027_Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - leaf diseases (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	2
	ESIM 028_Grass weed head cover (Grass weed head cover (%))	3
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	4
	ESIM PFC_C_8_Above canopy image (image)	5
GF	ESIM 070_Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index (Index)	1
	ESIM 112_Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	2
	ESIM 064_Nematode counts (counts/m3)	3
	ESIM PFC_C_8_Above canopy image (image)	4
	ESIM 004_Pan traps for beneficial insects (species list/index)	5

Recommendation 3: ES monitoring framework should consider the likely tradeoff between interpretability and sensitivity, with cost and efficiency. Considering how to use ESIMs in combination, or in sequence may aid in alleviating these tradeoffs.

Recommendation 4: System management indicators rely on appropriate practice – accurate checking for compaction, reduced disease pressure, or reduced N. The Theory of Change should consider the direct incentivization of the practice or the incentivization/legislation of the management index to encourage uptake of the practice.

Recommendation 5: Many ESIMs present the opportunity to be utilized as ground truthing for remote sensing development or image analysis, but perhaps beyond the scope of the current project.

Recommendation 6: Guidance on using ESIMs should include guidance on the appropriate interpretation of indicators depending on the indicator type and whether a counter-factual (i.e. on farm trials, field or farm comparisons etc.) are available.

1.5 Next Steps

The shortlisted indicators will form the focus of Deliverable 2.3 – ‘Practitioner protocols for measuring legume ESI’. Further efforts will be made to consider further details on the ESIMs, guided by requirements for WP6 activities and with further feedback from the legumES Participatory Farmer trials and Pilot Studies where possible. Potential additional evaluation criteria are listed in Table 11.

Table 11. Criterion 4) Additional criteria for integrating with WP6.

Additional questions for integrating with WP6	Answer
What is the smallest appropriate spatial scale to interpret the indicator?	Field; Farm; Regional.
What is the largest appropriate spatial scale to interpret the indicator?	Field; Farm; Regional.
What is the smallest appropriate temporal scale to interpret the indicator?	Growing season; crop rotation; beyond crop rotation.
What is the largest appropriate temporal scale to interpret the indicator?	Growing season; crop rotation; beyond crop rotation.
Can the indicator be linked to a quantifiable impact on on-farm decision making?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes - results can be used directly to inform a quantified benefit related to on-farm decision making e.g. reduction of required inputs (e.g., N rate, pesticide use, water use) or a quantification of increased productivity. • No - results can only be used to interpret direction of system change.
Threshold type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absolute threshold (e.g., fixed value, e.g. over 3%). • Relative threshold (must be compared to a similar system). • Trend based threshold (indicates a direction of change over time or space).

Additional questions for integrating with WP6	Answer
Is it likely this ES delivery can be modified by normal agricultural practice?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. • Yes - by altering legume genetics (species or variety). • Yes - by amending legume crop agronomic management (cultivation methods, seed rate, fert or ag-chem inputs etc). • Yes - by legume genetics or agronomic management.
ESI category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural (describes state of the system, e.g., SOC, veg cover). • Functional (describes a process, e.g., BNF rate, water infiltration rate).

References

- ADAS (2022) *GUIDE TO FARMERS' CROP TRIALS*. Available at: <https://farmpep.net/sites/default/files/2022-11/ADAS Farm Trials Guide updated Oct 2022.pdf>.
- AHDB (no date) *Monitoring dairy calf growth*. Available at: <https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/monitoring-dairy-calf-growth> (Accessed: 15 January 2025).
- Anglade, J., Billen, G. and Garnier, J. (2015) 'Relationships for estimating N₂ fixation in legumes: incidence for N balance of legume-based cropping systems in Europe', *Ecosphere*, 6(3), p. art37. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1890/ES14-00353.1>.
- Baddeley, J.A. *et al.* (2013) *Biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) by legume crops in Europe. Legume Futures Report 1.5*.
- Batur, F., Balazs, B. and Neulinger, A. (2025) *D.7.1 Policy Brief for the EU Horizon Europe funded project LegumES*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17944862>.
- Beauchêne, K. *et al.* (2023) *Deliverable 2.1 Phenotyping toolbox - Architectural traits*. Available at: https://root2res.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Root2Res_D2.1_ToolBox-ArchitecturalTraits_FINAL-1.pdf.
- Cimarelli, S. *et al.* (2025) 'Integrating ecosystem services provided by legumes in agricultural life cycle assessment (LCA): A review of methodologies', *Ecological Indicators*, 181, p. 114462. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.114462>.
- Cloy, J. *et al.* (no date) *Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure*. Available at: <https://www.sruc.ac.uk/media/xbrfn4x3/vess-colour-chart.pdf>.
- Constantin, J. *et al.* (2024) 'MERC: a simple method and decision-support tool to estimate availability of nitrogen from a wide range of cover crops to the next cash crop', *Plant and Soil*, 494(1), pp. 333–351. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-023-06283-1>.
- Defra (2023) *Harmonisation of Carbon Accounting Tools for Agriculture - SCF0129*. Available at: <https://sciencesearch.defra.gov.uk/ProjectDetails?ProjectId=20967>.
- DPIRD (no date) *Identifying soil compaction*. Available at: <https://www.agric.wa.gov.au/soil-compaction/identifying-soil-compaction> (Accessed: 15 January 2025).
- Hawes, C. (2022) *Farmland Biodiversity, Soil Health & Sustainability Assessment - A handbook of simple, on-farm indicators*. Available at: https://csc.hutton.ac.uk/resource/Handbook_of_indicators_v1.pdf.
- Hawes, C. *et al.* (2025) 'Long-term regenerative practices enhance in-field biodiversity and soil health for sustainable crop yields', *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, Volume 9-2025. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2025.1651686>.
- HGCA (2012) *Estimating Soil Nitrogen Supply (SNS). Topic Sheet 115/Summer 2012*. Available at: <https://farmpep.net/sites/default/files/2022-01/SNS Topic Sheet TS115.pdf>.
- Karley, A. *et al.* (2025) *LegumES multi-actor workshop for UK-based stakeholders and actors concerned with legume production and consumption. Part of Deliverable 1.1 for the EU Horizon Europe funded project LegumES*. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17646406>.
- Kiær, L. *et al.* (2020) *Handbook for trait assessment in agricultural plant teams. Deliverable report*

D2.2 (D17) *Handbook of protocols to assess traits in plant teams, developed by the EU-H2020 project DIVERSify ('Designing innovative plant teams for ecosystem resilience and agr. Available at: <https://plant-teams.org/#plottrials>.*

Kindred, D. *et al.* (2018) *Using farm experience to improve N management for wheat (LearN) - Project Report No. 596*. Available at: https://farmpep.net/sites/default/files/2022-01/LearN_pr596-final-project-report.pdf.

Mouritzen, T. *et al.* (2025) 'Faba bean genetics and crop growth models – progress to date and opportunities for integration', *Plant and Soil*, 514, pp. 47–64. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-025-07459-7>.

Newall Price, P. *et al.* (2020) *Deliverable 2.2b - Quantifying ecosystem services on permanent Grassland - A short list of agri-environmental indicators. SUPER-G*. Available at: https://www.super-g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/SUPER-G_D2-2-Report_Final.pdf.

NUTRI-CHECK NET Platform (no date). Available at: <https://platform.nutri-checknet.eu/>.

Palmer, R.C. and Smith, R.P. (2013) 'Soil structural degradation in SW England and its impact on surface-water runoff generation', *Soil Use and Management*, 29(4), pp. 567–575. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12068>.

Ritz, K. *et al.* (2009) 'Selecting biological indicators for monitoring soils: A framework for balancing scientific and technical opinion to assist policy development', *Ecological Indicators*, 9(6), pp. 1212–1221. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2009.02.009>.

Soilmentor (no date a) *Infiltration Rate*. Available at: <https://soils.vidacycle.com/soil-tests/1-3-infiltration-rate/> (Accessed: 15 January 2025).

Soilmentor (no date b) *Slake (Wet Aggregate Stability)*. Available at: <https://soils.vidacycle.com/soil-tests/1-2-slake-0-8/> (Accessed: 15 January 2025).

UK Pollinator Monitoring Scheme (no date) *FIT Counts: help us monitor pollinators*. Available at: <https://ukpoms.org.uk/fit-counts> (Accessed: 15 January 2025).

Wall, D., Redmond, C. and Kendall, S. (2023) *Deliverable 1.2 Report: Drivers, needs, challenges and barriers for farmers to improve arable crop nutrition and the adoption of nutrient management decision tools and technologies, for the NUTRI-CHECK NET Project*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e506b3d0ef&appId=PPGMS>.

White, C. *et al.* (2022) 'The Bean YEN: Understanding bean yield variation on UK farms', *Annals of Applied Biology*, 181(2), pp. 137–151. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/aab.12768>.

Appendix

Gross list of indicator methods

Table Annex 1. List of Ecosystem Service Indicator Methods (ESIMs) which underwent full logical sieve challenge criteria screening following initial pre-screening for potential use by end users.

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 003	Pollinator transects	Number of pollinators scored (counts/m)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	Y
ESIM 004	Pan traps for beneficial insects	Abundance or presence of target beneficial species; Biodiversity index (species list/index)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	Y
ESIM 006	Earthworm surveys	Earthworm abundance (counts/m ³)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	Y
ESIM 008	Tea bags for litter decomposition	Decomposition rate ((g) lost / day)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	Y
ESIM 009	Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS)	Soil Structural score (Scale (1-5))	Expert elicitation, method reference: (Cloy <i>et al.</i>)	Y
ESIM 010	Soil organic matter content (LOI)	Soil organic matter content (%/kg dry soil)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 011	Slake test	Soil aggregate stability ((g) lost)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (Soilmentor)	Y
ESIM 012	Water infiltration	Percolation time (ml/s)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (Soilmentor a)	Y
ESIM 013	Flower Insect Timed counts	Number of floral visits by insects (visits/minute)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (UK Pollinator Monitoring Scheme)	Y
ESIM 014	Observed soil erosion risk	Presence of erosion features (Y/N & severity)	Adapted from Palmer and Smith, (2013); Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	Y
ESIM 015	Following crop soil N supply - measured uptake	Crop N content (Kg N/ha) (Kg N/ha)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (HGCA, 2012)	Y
ESIM 023	Grain yield	Grain yield (t/ha)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 024	Grain Protein Content	Grain protein content (crude) (Kg/ha)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 025	Grain amino acid profile	Grain amino acid profile (%)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 026	Soil mineral N content	Soil mineral N content (Kg NO ₃ - & NH ₃ /ha)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 027	Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - leaf diseases	Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9)	(Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
		(Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))		
ESIM 028	Grass weed head cover	Weed head density (Grass weed head cover (%) Grass weed head density (seed heads/m ²))	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 029	Weed vegetation surveys	Weed density (%)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 030	Following crop yield	Yield (t/ha & moisture content (%))	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 032	Following crop nutrient concentration - grain nutrient analysis	Grain nutrient concentration (N (% of dry seed biomass) and/or for P, K, Mg, S, Zn, Mo, Cu, Fe, Ca)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 034	Carbon calculators	Yield per unit area per Kg CO ₂ e (CO ₂ e/t/ha)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 035	Land use efficiency ratios	Land use efficiency ratio (Ratio)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 036	Range testing N rates	Economic optimum N rate - on farm testing (Kg N/ha)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (Kindred <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	Y
ESIM 038	Yield stability calculation	% deviation from average yield (%)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 039	Flower cover and duration	Flower cover and duration (% and start and end date)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 040	Non-harvested residue N content - measured	N in residues returned to soil (Kg N/ha)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 041	Non-harvested residue N content - estimated from biomass (weight)	N in residues returned to soil (Kg N/ha)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (Anglade, Billen and Garnier, 2015)	Y
ESIM 042	Non-harvested residue N content - estimated from yield	N in residues returned to soil (Kg N/ha)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (Baddeley <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	Y
ESIM 044	Non-harvested residue N content - modelled	N in residues returned to soil (Kg N/ha)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 045	Quality - visual appearance	Quality - visual appearance - % acceptability (%)	Pilot Study 5	Y
ESIM 046	Bird monitoring	Farmland bird index (index)	Pilot Study 21	Y
ESIM 047	Soil eDNA microbiome analysis	biodiversity indexes (index)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 048	Soil microbial respiration - Solvita CO ₂ soil burst	CO ₂ soil burst (ppm)	Expert elicitation	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 052	Following crop nutrient concentration - leaf nutrient analysis	N (% of dry leaf biomass) and/or for P, K, Mg, S, Zn, Mo, Cu, Fe, Ca (%)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 055	N use efficiency calculations	N input per unit produce (Kg N/t)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 056	Shovelomics	max rooting depth; RLD at depth (cm; cam root per cm ³ soil)	(Beauchêne <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	Y
ESIM 058	Soil nutrients - exchangeable P, K, Mg	pH, P, K, Mg (mg exchangeable nutrient/kg soil) (mg/kg OR nutrient recommendation system index (index may differ between country))	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 060	Soil penetration resistance - penetrometer	Maximum penetrometer reading (PSI) to 30 cm soil depth Maximum penetrometer reading (PSI) to full soil depth Depth (mm) to threshold value (PSI & mm)	Expert elicitation, method reference: (DPIRD)	Y
ESIM 061	Water consumption rates	Water consumption rates (Number of watering days, total water rate (l/ha/day), the cost of water (Euro/l).)	Plot Study 24	Y
ESIM 062	Soil moisture content - probes	Water fraction by volume (%)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 064	Nematode counts	Nematode counts (counts/m ³)	Plot Study 24	Y
ESIM 065	Above ground biomass - estimated from yield and HI	Above ground biomass (t dm/ha)	Pilot Study 5 (White <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Y
ESIM 068	Ground cover - imagery	Percentage ground cover (%)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Y
ESIM 070	Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index	Pesticide Treatment Frequency Index (Index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Y
ESIM 071	Floral unit density for Estimation of nectariferous value from abundance of different flowers from plant species	Floral unit density (Floral units/m ² (per each plant species))	Adapted from UK Pollinator Monitoring Scheme and Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , (2025)	Y
ESIM 072	Degree of Compaction (DC) - visual from soil cores	Visual soil compaction score (Score)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Y
ESIM 073	Water use efficiency	Water use per unit produce (m ³ h ₂ O/t)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 076	Sweep netting for predatory insects	Abundance or presence of target beneficial species; Biodiversity index (species list/index)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 077	Buffer strip size and quality	% of buffer strips, trees, hedges, areas for non-agricultural land use on field level (length per km ² OR % area)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 078	Ground cover - visual estimation	Ground cover (%)	(Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 079	Tractor mounted N sensors	Spectral reflectance converted to a recommended N rate (Kg/ha) (Spectral indices OR Kg/ha)	(NUTRI-CHECK NET Platform)	Y
ESIM 080	Grain protein analysis - following crops	Grain protein content (crude) (%)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 081	Nil N plot in following crop coupled with in season monitoring of N requirement	NUE index	(NUTRI-CHECK NET Platform)	Y
ESIM 083	Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - stem diseases	Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9) (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	Adapted from (Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 084	Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - root diseases	Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9) (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	Adapted from (Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 085	Disease incidence and severity in other crop species - foliar diseases	Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9) (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	Adapted from (Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 086	Pest incidence and severity in other crop species - stem boring pests	Pest or disease incidence (%) Larvae per stem (count/plant) (Pest or disease incidence (%) Larvae per stem (count/plant))	Adapted from (Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 087	Pest incidence and severity in other crop species - leaf mining/grazing pests	Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9) (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	Adapted from (Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 088	Pest incidence and severity in other crop species - aphids	Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9) (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	Adapted from (Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 089	"soil health" analysis - e.g Haney test	Soil health index (index)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 090	Soil microbial diversity analysis - PLFA	Soil microbial biomass (mg PLFA/kg soil)	Expert elicitation	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 091	Forage or Feed efficiency - Milk production	Daily milk yield (litres/cow)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 092	Forage or silage quality for feed	Multiple metrics available depending on livestock and quality aspect of interest, including dry matter, pH, ash, crude protein, metabolizable energy (Multiple)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 097	Refractometer	Brix index (calibration may be required for each plant species) (index)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 098	Soil electrical conductivity	Electrical Conductivity (ds/M)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 110	Potential mineralizable N	Kg NO ₃ - & NH ₃ /ha, available and potential (Kg NO ₃ - & NH ₃ /ha, available and potential)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 112	Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover	Above ground botanical biodiversity and percentage ground cover (species index; %)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 114	Mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) carbon fractions	mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) C:N percent change (C %/kg dry soil)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 115	POM carbon fractions	particulate organic matter (POM) (SOC %/kg dry soil)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 116	Labile soil carbon - permanganate-oxidizable carbon (POXC)	permanganate-oxidizable carbon (POXC) (SOC %/kg dry soil)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 117	Testing soils for legume fatigue	Foot rot complex risk (Risk score)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 120	Soil organic carbon - Dumas method	Soil organic carbon - Dumas method (SOC %/kg dry soil)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 123	Sward grazing value - estimated from biomass - rising plate	Sward grazing value (kg DM/ha and species composition)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 125	Ground cover image assessment with machine learning model	Ground cover (%)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Y
ESIM 129	Seed set counting of "supported" crops	Number of seeds set (seeds/m ²)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Y
ESIM 143	N uptake by catch crops/ Nil N fertilised cereals	Soil N Supply (Kg N/ha)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Y
ESIM 147	Grass utilisation by livestock	Grass utilisation (the proportion of grass dry matter grown that is consumed by livestock) (%)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 149	N use efficiency (fertiliser)	N use efficiency (fertiliser) (% (N input/N output))	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 151	Gross-margin analysis	Gross margin (£ per ha OR £ per head)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 154	Categories extensive /intensive land use	Categories extensive /intensive land use (measured in LU/ha) (LU/ha of total UAA)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 157	Utilization of grass from grazing	Utilization of grass from grazing (%)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 160	Mechanical weed management	Mechanical weed management (Y/N)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 161	Sward/fallow mowing date	1st date of mowing (date)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 162	Grass cutting frequency	Grass cutting frequency (management intensity) (number of cuts)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 163	Length of grazing season	Length of grazing season (days) (days)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 164	Stocking rate (grazing livestock)	Stocking rate (grazing livestock) (LU/ha of TG + PG) (LU/ha of TG + PG)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 165	Milk urea concentration	Milk urea concentration (mg/l) (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 166	Minimum mowing height	Minimum mowing height (cm) (cm)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 167	Maximum mowing height	Maximum mowing height (cm) (cm)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 178	Number of nesting sites for meadow birds	Number of nesting sites for meadow birds (number/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 179	Mole hills	Mole hills (per yr/per ha) (mole hills/ha OR mole hills/ha/yr)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 188	Mineral N fertiliser application rate	Mineral N fertiliser application rate (kg N/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 197	Quantity and composition of livestock feed	Quantity and composition of livestock feed (t concentrate/yr OR estimated milk from grass (litres milk/cow))	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 198	Grass sward age	Age of the grass sward (years) (Years)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 200	Thickness of peat layer	Thickness of peat layer (m) (metres)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 213	N surplus on soil surface balance	N surplus on soil surface balance (kg N/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 214	P surplus on soil surface balance	P surplus on soil surface balance (kg P/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 215	N input rate	N input rate (manufactured fertiliser N rate plus effective (fertiliser equiv.) manure N rate) (kg N/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 216	P input rate	P input rate (sum of total P in manufactured fertiliser and manure) (kg P/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 225	Ponding, standing water	Ponding, standing water (Y/N OR % area)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 227	Quantities of manure applied	Quantities of manure applied (t/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 228	Proportion of legumes in the grass sward	Legumes in the grass sward (%)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 230	Length of ditches	Length of ditches (m/ha) (m/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 231	Livestock access to watercourses (y/n)	Livestock access to watercourses (y/n) (Y/N)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 240	Sealing / crusting presence	Sealing / crusting presence (Y/N or %)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 255	Number/Presence of erosion features (rills, gullies, landslides) - 1- Evidence of surface runoff / erosion pedestals / sediment deposition; 2- Evidence of rills; 3- Presence of gullies or eroded stream banks; 4- Presence of landslides/mass wasting; 5- Presence of piping	Number/Presence of erosion features (rills, gullies, landslides) - 1- Evidence of surface runoff / erosion pedestals / sediment deposition; 2- Evidence of rills; 3- Presence of gullies or eroded stream banks; 4- Presence of landslides/mass wasting; 5- Presence of piping (Y/N)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 258	European tourist roads	European tourist roads (presence/absence or length)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 259	Nature trails	Nature trails (presence/absence or length)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 260	Bicycle roads	Bicycle roads (presence/absence or length)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 261	Riding trails	Riding trails (presence/absence or length)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 262	Viewpoints (look-out tower or prominence by relief)	Viewpoints (look-out tower or prominence by relief) (number per 10 km ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 263	Visitor centres (on the spot or neighbouring)	Visitor centres (on the spot or neighbouring) (number per 10 km ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 264	Open-air school (on the spot or neighbouring)	Open-air school (on the spot or neighbouring) (number per 10 km ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 265	Tourist hotels (on the spot or neighbouring)	Tourist hotels (on the spot or neighbouring) (number per 10 km ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 266	Fishing-places (on the spot or neighbouring)	Fishing-places (on the spot or neighbouring) (number per 10 km ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 268	Natural heritage, sacred objects connected to nature, huge trees etc.	Natural heritage, sacred objects connected to nature, huge trees etc. (number per 10 km ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 269	Number of photos on the area by a social media (e.g. flickR)	Number of photos on the area by a social media (e.g. flickR) (number of photos)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 270	Buffer strip size and quality	% of buffer strips, trees, hedges, areas for non-agricultural land use on field level (length per km ² OR % area)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 271	Landscape - state and diversity	Landscape - state and diversity (tree lines, hedges, stone wall) (length per km ² OR Y/N)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM 273	Pods per plant as pod set success	Pods per plant as pod set success (Pods/plant)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 279	Cotton strip assay for measuring litter decomposition	Decomposition rate ((g) lost / day)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	Y
ESIM 280	Hydrogen Peroxide test	Organic matter content (Scale (low, medium, high))	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 281	Sward grazing value - estimated from biomass - quadrat	Sward grazing value (kg DM/ha and species composition)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 301	Nodulation score	Average nodule number per plant; average nodule size per plant; presence of active nodules; nodule score (1-9) (Proportion of pink nodules; proportion of large nodules; number of nodules)	(Beauchêne <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	Y
ESIM 302	Seed quality as feed	Multiple metrics available depending on livestock and quality aspect of interest, including: Grain amino acid profile, grain crude protein content; fibre; starch; moisture; ash content; mineral nutrients; oil etc & calculation of nutritional	Expert elicitation	Y

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
		indices relevant to livestock type (Multiple)		
ESIM 303	Plant density/plant population	Plant population (Plants/m ²)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM 304	End market value of legume seed	Price of product (Euros/t)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM PFC_C_1	Yield – seed - commercial combine harvester	Yield – seed (t/ha & moisture content (%))	Expert elicitation, method reference (ADAS, 2022)	Y
ESIM PFC_C_2	Yield – seed- quadrats	Yield – seed (t/ha & moisture content (%))	Adapted from (Kiær <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Y
ESIM PFC_C_3	Yield– forage crops - quadrats	Yield– forage (t/ha & moisture content (%))	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM PFC_C_5	Flowering duration	Start and end date of flowering (DD/MM/YYYY) (Dates)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM PFC_C_6	Days to maturity	Date of sowing, date of emergence, date of ripe to harvest & actual harvest date (DD/MM/YYYY) (Dates)	Expert elicitation	Y
ESIM PFC_C_8	Above canopy image	Above canopy image (image)	Expert elicitation	Y

Table Annex 2. List of Ecosystem Service Indicator Methods (ESIMs) which were excluded from full logical sieve challenge criteria screening following initial pre-screening for potential use by end users.

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 1	Arable weed diversity	Number of weed species (counts/m ²)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	N
ESIM 2	Soil seedbank diversity	Emerged weed species list (species list)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	N
ESIM 5	Pitfall traps for predatory insects	Abundance or presence of target beneficial species; Biodiversity index (species list/index)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	N
ESIM 7	Soil microarthropod diversity	Soil microarthropod diversity (species list/index)	Pilot Study 1 (Hawes, 2022)	N
ESIM 17	N fixation N difference method	BNF rate (% Ndfa)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 18	N fixation 15N dilution method	BNF rate (% Ndfa)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 20	Forage or Feed efficiency - Livestock daily live weight gain	Daily live weight gain (Growth rate (kg/day))	Pilot Study 6: Method reference (AHDB,)	N
ESIM 31	Soil erosion pins	Soil Erosion Rate (mm/year)	Pilot Study 31	N
ESIM 33	Preference surveys	% choice or ratings (% choice or ratings)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 37	Chlorophyll fluorescence	SPAD score can be converted to N content by species specific calibration score (Index)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 53	Resilience to soil compaction		Pilot Study 2	N
ESIM 66	Above ground biomass - quadrat	Above ground biomass (t dm/ha)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 69	Evidence of predated insects - parasitized aphids	Presence of parasitised aphids (Y/N)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 74	Camera traps	Presence of small mammals (Y/N)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 82	Spectral reflectance of following crops to adjust within season nutrient rates	Spectral reflectance converted to a recommended N rate (Kg/ha) (Spectral indices OR Kg N/ha)	Adapted from (NUTRI-CHECK NET Platform, no date)	N
ESIM 93	Soil nitrate sensors	Nitrate in water (mmol NO ₃ - or mg/l)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 99	Preference surveys	% choice or ratings (% choice or ratings)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 101	Pollen value (composition)	Amino acid profile	Expert elicitation	N

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 102	Presence of extra floral nectar	Presence of extra floral nectar (Y/N)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 106	Soil phosphate sensors	Soil phosphate concentration (mg/l)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 107	Camera traps	Presence of pollinators (Y/N)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 111	Greenhouse gas measurements	CO ₂ e derived from CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O concentrations (CO ₂ e/t and CO ₂ e/ha)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 118	Aggregate stability in water	Aggregate stability (e.g. soil dispersion ratio) (proportion, by weight, of silt and clay suspended by mild slaking forces to the total amount present in the sample (ranges given for different stability classes))	Pilot Study 2	N
ESIM 119	water holding capacity after 24 and 48h drainage	Available water holding capacity (mm)	Pilot Study 2	N
ESIM 121	Bee identification	Presence/absence of species, species list (Y/N; species list)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 122	Food mineral analysis	bio-available minerals (mg/g)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 126	Root biomass measurement from soil samples	Below ground biomass (t dm/ha)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 128	Soil moisture - gravimetric	Soil moisture content (%)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 130	Hierarchical richness index	biodiversity indexes (index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 131	IndVal index	biodiversity indexes (index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 133	Sampling with Blow&Vac leaf-blower apparatus converted to suction sampler	Abundance or presence of target beneficial species; Biodiversity index (species list/index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 134	Shannon diversity index	biodiversity indexes (index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 135	Shannon evenness index	biodiversity indexes (index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 136	Sørensen similarity index	biodiversity indexes (index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 137	Species richness (Whittaker et al. 2001)	biodiversity indexes (index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 138	Analysis of mycorrhizal root colonization with intersect method (McGonigle et al. 1990)	Root length colonisation (%)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 139	Herbivorous insects sampling - miscellaneous (e.g stem dissection for boring insects, pheromone traps etc)	incidence/severity (Pest or disease incidence (%) Pest or disease severity (1-9))	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 140	Margalef index on weed species	biodiversity indexes (index)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 141	BNF estimates with (Korsaeth and Eltun, 2000) method	BNF rate (% Ndfa)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 142	Linear relationships between BNF and shoot N	BNF total (Kg N/ha)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 144	Sattelite spectral reflectance on legume crop	Spectral reflectance converted to biomass (indices; t dm/ha)	(Cimarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	N
ESIM 169	Presence of a threatened species associated with grassland (CR, EN or VU) – from list of 351 species associated with grassland in Europe	Presence of a threatened species associated with grassland (CR, EN or VU) – from list of 351 species associated with grassland in Europe (Y/N)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 172	Presence of key cultural – charismatic – species (e.g. those grassland species of value to people)	Presence of key cultural – charismatic – species (e.g. those grassland species of value to people) (Y/N)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 176	Earthworm biomass	Earthworm biomass (g/m ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 177	Botanical composition	Botanical composition (% cover of each species)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 180	Dung beetle numbers	Dung beetle numbers (per ha) (number/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 199	Peatland rate of subsidence	Peatland rate of subsidence (cm/yr) (cm/yr)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 203	Porous pots	Nitrate-N concentration in groundwater (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 204	Porous pots	Nitrate-N concentration in surface water (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 205	Porous pots	Nitrate-N concentration in drainwater (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 206	Ortho-P concentration in surface water	Ortho-P concentration in surface water (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
ESIM 207	Ortho-P concentration in groundwater	Ortho-P concentration in groundwater (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 208	Ortho-P concentration in drainwater	Ortho-P concentration in drainwater (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 209	Particulate P in surface water	Particulate P in surface water (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 210	Pesticide concentration in surface water	Pesticide concentration in surface water (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 211	Pesticide concentration in drainwater	Pesticide concentration in drainwater (µg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 212	Heavy metals concentration in surface water	Heavy metals concentration in surface water (µg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 218	Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)	Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) (mg/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 220	Sediment load (Overlap with ES Erosion Control)	Sediment load (Overlap with ES Erosion Control) (t sediment/day or mg sediment/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 221	Stream flow rate in critical periods	Stream flow rate in critical periods (?) as a measure of water infiltration & retention (m ³ /s)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 222	Surface water turbidity	Surface water turbidity (Formazin Turbidity Unit (FTU))	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 223	Number of eutrophication incidents per year	Number of eutrophication incidents per year (incidents/year)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 224	Biological status of rivers with and without sewage treatment works	Biological status of rivers with and without sewage treatment works (status (red, amber, green); various metrics)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 226	Algae as bioindicators of water quality	Algae as bioindicators of water quality (Presence & abundance of bioindicator species)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 229	Groundwater table	Groundwater table (cm depth) (cm depth)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 232	Bulk density (FDR and VIS-NIR spectroscopy method)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 233	Vegetation cover / Bare soil (NDVI-Sentinel)	Vegetation cover / Bare soil (NDVI-Sentinel) (%)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 235	Depth of soil	Depth of soil (cm)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 236	Hydraulic conductivity, soil sorbtivity and soil matrix flux potential (e.g. the	Hydraulic conductivity, soil sorbtivity and soil matrix flux potential (mm/h)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N

No.	Indicator Method	Indicator (Units)	Source (project, task, Pilot Study or expert elicitation)	Pre-screening result
	Guelph permeameter or Mini Disk Infiltrometer)			
ESIM 238	Soil moisture storage capacity	Moisture storage capacity (mm/m or mm/cm)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 239	Packing density	Packing density (kg/cm ³)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 241	Shear strength (Going Stick method)	Shear strength (Going Stick method) (kPa)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 242	Shear strength (shear vane method)	Shear strength (shear vane method) (kPa)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 246	Bulk density (Kopecki ring)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 247	Erodibility (USLE's K-factor)	Erodibility (USLE's K-factor) (quantitative description (factor))	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 250	Annual soil erosion rate by water (t soil/ha)	Annual soil erosion rate by water (t soil/ha) (t soil/ha)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 251	Sediment load	Sediment load (t sediment/day or mg sediment/l)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 252	Runoff coefficient	Runoff coefficient (ratio of runoff to rainfall) (coefficient between 0.0 and 1.0)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 254	S index	S index (Dexter's soil physical quality index; the inflection point of a soil water retention curve) (index)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 267	Geocaching points	Geocaching points (number per 10 km ²)	(Newall Price <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	N
ESIM 272	Economic optimum N rate - small plot N response curve	Economic optimum N rate (Kg N/ha)	Pilot Study 30	N
ESIM 274	Soil porosity	ratio of nonsolid volume to the total volume of soil (Ratio)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 275	Partial LER	Partial LER (Ratio)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 276	Total Overyielding Index	Total Overyielding Index (Ratio)	Expert elicitation	N
ESIM 277	Soil surface N balance	Soil surface N balance (Kg/N)	Pilot Study 30	N
ESIM 278	Non-harvested residue N content - estimated from biomass (spectral reflectance)	N in residues returned to soil (Kg N/ha)	Pilot Study 30	N